

Research Data Management - Onboarding @IOER

Research Data Management (RDM) is a cross-functional, multi-level and multidisciplinary endeavour shared among various actors across the research data life cycle. Like a Jigsaw, RDM requires multiple pieces of knowledge and competencies. The Onboarding RDM Checklist introduces the new staff to RDM, providing the initial information and knowledge bricks to FAIRly manage the research data along the project lifecycle, ensuring compliance with policies and best practices adoption.

Checklist

Topics	To Dos	Sources
Training		
<i>RDM Seminar</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Schedule participation IOER RDM Seminar <input type="checkbox"/> Review training material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check the IOER RDM info (Intranet) • IOER RDM Seminar Slides
High-Level Policies		
<i>Relevant RDM policies</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Review high-level policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IOER Good Scientific Practice • Leibniz - Open Access Policy • Leibniz - Handling of Research Data • Leibniz - FAIR data • CoARA agreement • DORA declaration
Best Practices & Knowledge bricks		
<i>Data Management Planning (DMP) & Research Output Management Planning</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Review Template Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi) <input type="checkbox"/> Review Research Output Lifecycle - Guidance for the Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Template - Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi) • Guidance - Research Output Lifecycle • IOER Data Steward provides templates and support
<i>Naming Conventions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Review file naming convention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IOER Naming Convention
<i>PIDs</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Create your ORCID	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORCID
<i>Algorithm coding</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Create a GitHub account <input type="checkbox"/> Link GitHub and Zenodo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GitHub • Link GitHub and Zenodo • GitLab (TU Chemnitz)

	<input type="checkbox"/> Register GitLab account (TU Chemnitz) <input type="checkbox"/> Review coding best practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coding best practices
<i>Review storage and available collaborative tools</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Review backup and storage <input type="checkbox"/> Review SharePoint info in the Intranet <input type="checkbox"/> Review FILR info in the Intranet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IOER RDM Storage, Backup & Recovery • TU-Dresden SharePoint (Intranet) • FILR (Intranet)
<i>Reference Manager Software</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Review the Reference Manager SW supported by IOER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get started with the IOER Zotero Institutional subscription (Intranet) • To date, EndNote licenses are available; ask the IT (Intranet).
<i>Collaborative communication</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Setup Element for collaborative communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How-to guidance for the Element desktop app
Sharing and Repository		
<i>IOER FDZ</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Review FDZ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FDZ Website and info
<i>Zenodo</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Create Zenodo account <input type="checkbox"/> Review the IOER Zenodo Community <input type="checkbox"/> Review the upload guidance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zenodo • IOER Zenodo Community • Zenodo how-to-upload Guidance
<i>Licenses</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Review the Creative Commons Licenses <input type="checkbox"/> Review Open Access Info	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative Common • IOER Open Access info (Intranet)
<i>Publication reporting</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Review how to register any published output with the internal registration form	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check the internal publication registration process (Intranet): → Online-Formular